

Impact of behavioral aspects of Autism on cognitive abilities in children with autism spectrum disorder

Authors : Rana M. Zeina, Laila AL-Ayadhi, and Shahid Bashir

Abstract : Cognitive symptoms and behavioral symptoms may, in fact, overlap and be related to the level of the general cognitive function. We have measured the behavioral aspects of autism and its correlation to the cognitive ability in 30 ASDs children who In this study, we used a neuropsychological battery to evaluate children with ASDs who received the AAC intervention compared to the ASD group who did not since cognitive computerized batteries provide a better assessment of cognitive ability in this study. Five visual memory tests of Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB) including Big/little circle (BLC), Motor screening (MOT), Intra/Extra dimensional set shift (IED), Simple Reaction Time (SRT), and Spatial recognition memory (SRM) were administered to 30 children with ASD and behavioral problems aged 6 to 11 who did not receive the AAC with an IQ mean of 62. Individuals with ASD and challenging behaviors showed significant correlation between Lethargy and big little circle (BLC), Lethargy and Intra/Extra set shift (IED). Significant correlation was also found between Hyperactivity, Simple Reaction Time (SRT), and Intra/Extra set shift (IED). With regards to stereotypy and Motor (MOT), there was a significant correlation between both of them. There was also a significant correlation between Inappropriate Speech and Motor (MOT). Based on these findings, we can conclude that the behavioral problems in autism affect specific cognitive abilities in ASDs comprehension, learning, reversal, acquisition, attention set shifting, and speed of reaction to one stimulus.

Keywords : Cognitive ability, Neuropsychological test, Behavioral motor aspects, and Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASDs).

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